
e3dmt Documentation

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E3DMT version 1 package is a program library for carrying out forward modelling and inversion of magnetotelluric and Z-axis tipper EM data 3D. The contents of this manual are as follows:

E3DMT VERSION 1 PACKAGE OVERVIEW

1.1 Description

This manual provides instructions and background information for the E3DMT version 1 program library. This library is capable of forward modeling and inverting magnetotelluric and ZTEM data. E3DMT is built in the same manner as E3D, so much of the background presented in this manual is identical to the E3D manual. In order to decrease computational time and increase accuracy by mesh refinement in areas of interest, conductivity models are discretized on an Octree mesh.

Fig. 1.1: 2D (QuadTree) mesh discretization about a ring (left). Cell refinement for OcTree mesh (right).

The program library has utilities for generating OcTree meshes and conductivity models. From the users point of view the software operates in much the same way as previous GIF codes. Both codes can be run from the command line or through the GIFtools GUI.

Both program libraries provide codes to do the following:

1. Create OcTree meshes based on the survey geometry
2. Construct models on OcTree meshes, where each cell is assigned a constant value of conductivity.
3. Forward model magnetotelluric and ZTEM data resulting from a particular conductivity model.
4. Invert surface (MT), airborne (ZTEM) data to generate 3D conductivity models:

- The inversion is solved as an optimization problem with the simultaneous goals of (i) minimizing an objective function dependent on the model and (ii) generating synthetic data that match observations to within a degree of misfit consistent with the statistics of those data.
- To counteract the inherent lack of information, the formulation incorporates reference model and smoothing by regularization.
- Capacity for the user to directionally weight smoothing and reference model influence as well as overall influence of regularization on objective function minimization. Explicit prior information may also take the form of upper and lower bounds on the conductivity contrast in any cell.
- The regularization parameter (controlling relative importance of objective function and misfit terms).

The initial research underlying the E3DMT version 1 (2014) library was funded principally by the mineral industry consortium Joint and Cooperative Inversion of Geophysical and Geological Data” (1991 - 1997) which was sponsored by NSERC and the following 11 companies: BHP Minerals, CRA Exploration, Cominco Exploration, Falconbridge, Hudson Bay Exploration and Development, INCO Exploration & Technical Services, Kennecott Exploration Company, Newmont Gold Company, Noranda Exploration, Placer Dome, and WMC.

Since then, improvements have been implemented as time and resources permit.

1.2 Program Library Content

The main executable programs within the E3DMT version 1 program library are:

- **e3dmt_fwd**: Solves the forward problem. Computes the electric and magnetic response to a 3D conductivity model (fields, and impedance)
- **e3dmt**: Solves the inverse problem using a direct solver approach (MUMPS). Recovers a conductivity model by inverting MT or ZTEM data. All entries of the impedance tensor or transfer function are needed.
- **e3dmt_iter**: Solves the inverse problem using an iterative solver approach. Recovers a conductivity model by inverting MT or ZTEM data. All entries of the impedance tensor or transfer function are needed.
- **create_octree_mesh_e3dmt**: Creates an octree mesh based on the *survey file*

Common Octree utility programs used with this package include:

- **blk3cell**: Creates models from a set of blocks on a tensor mesh
- **3DModel2Octree**: Converts models from tensor to Octree meshes
- **interface_weights**: Creates interface weights

1.3 Licensing

Licensing for commercial use is managed by distributors, not by the UBC-GIF research group.

1.4 Installation

1.4.1 E3DMT Executables

There is no automatic installer currently available for E3DMT version 1. Please follow the following steps in order to use the software:

1. Extract all files provided from the given zip-based archive and place them all together in a new folder.
2. Add this directory as new path to your environment variables.
3. Make sure to create a separate directory for each new inversion, where all the associated files will be stored. Do not store anything in the bin directory other than executable applications and Graphical User Interface applications (GUIs).

1.4.2 MPI Executables

Message passaging interface (MPI) programming allows E3DMT version 1 to utilize parallel computing. Even if the code is being run on a single machine, the user is **required** to download the necessary MPI package to use the E3DMT version 1 executables. To set up MPI:

1. Download and install:
 - [Microsoft MPI v10.0](#) : Required for window machines
 - [MPICH](#) : Required for Linux machines
2. Path the folders containing MPI executables to your environment variables.

BACKGROUND THEORY

This section aims to provide the user with a basic review of the physics, discretization, and optimization techniques used to solve the frequency domain quasi-static electromagnetics problem. It is assumed that the user has some background in these areas. For further reading see [Nab91].

Important:

The theory provided on this page works for the following right-handed coordinate systems:

- X = Easting, Y = Northing, Z = Up (standard Cartesian)
 - X = Northing, Y = Easting, Z = Down (standard magnetotelluric which this code uses!)
-

2.1 Fundamental Physics

Maxwell's equations provide the starting point from which an understanding of how electromagnetic fields can be used to uncover the substructure of the Earth. In the frequency domain Maxwell's equations are:

$$\begin{aligned}\nabla \times \mathbf{E} - i\omega\mu\mathbf{H} &= 0 \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{H} - \sigma\mathbf{E} &= \mathbf{J}_s\end{aligned}\tag{2.1}$$

where \mathbf{E} and \mathbf{H} are the electric and magnetic fields, \mathbf{J}_s is some external source and $e^{-i\omega t}$ is suppressed. Symbols μ , σ and ω are the magnetic permeability, conductivity, and angular frequency, respectively. This formulation assumes a quasi-static mode so that the system can be viewed as a diffusion equation (Weaver, 1994; Ward and Hohmann, 1988 in [Nab91]). By doing so, some difficulties arise when solving the system;

- the curl operator has a non-trivial null space making the resulting linear system highly ill-conditioned
- the conductivity σ varies over several orders of magnitude

2.2 Natural Sources: MT and ZTEM

The sources in the magnetotelluric (MT) and Z-axis tipper electromagnetic (ZTEM) methods are modeled as plane waves originating from natural phenomenon. These waves can be of very low frequency (< 1 Hz) and very high energy, making it possible to image very deep targets. This also implies that the source term is zero inside the domain of interest, and therefore the source term on the boundaries becomes very important. For natural source electromagnetic (NSEM) problems, we solve the following system:

$$\begin{aligned}\nabla \times \mathbf{E} - i\omega\mu\mathbf{H} &= 0 \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{H} - \sigma\mathbf{E} &= \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{E}|_{\partial\Omega} &= \mathbf{0}\end{aligned}\tag{2.1}$$

where \mathbf{E}_0 is the electric field solution on the boundary $\partial\Omega$.

Consider the case where the Earth is a uniform half-space with a plane surface. If the source field is assumed to be homogeneous, infinite in dimension, and is located at infinity, then the plane waves impinging on the Earth's surface travel in the z-direction.

For plane waves polarized such that their electric fields lie along the x direction, the electric field is defined by the following Helmholtz equation:

$$\frac{\partial^2 E_x}{\partial z^2} = k^2 E_x \quad \text{s.t.} \quad k^2 = -i\omega\mu\sigma \quad (2.1)$$

and the relationship between E_x and H_y is given by:

$$i\omega\mu H_y = \frac{\partial E_x}{\partial z} \quad (2.2)$$

The solution to (2.1) takes the form:

$$E_x = Qe^{-kz} \quad (2.3)$$

where Q is some constant. Taking the ratio of the electric and magnetic fields measured at the surface gives:

$$Z_{xy} = \frac{E_x}{H_y} = \frac{-i\omega\mu}{k} = \sqrt{\frac{-i\omega\mu}{\sigma}} \quad (2.4)$$

This implies that conductivity σ of the Earth can be determined by taking measurements of the field components, and therefore the impedance constitutes the basic MT response function, or data. A 1D layered Earth model can be used to compute the source wave components by iteratively propagating a plane wave from the surface to depth.

2.2.1 Magnetotelluric (MT) Data

For a 3-dimensional Earth, the magnetotelluric data are defined by the impedance tensor. The impedance tensor can be defined using the ratios of electric and magnetic field components in both the x and y directions for 2 orthogonal plane wave polarizations; one polarization with the electric field along the x axis and one polarization with the electric field along the y axis. Where the impedance tensor \mathbf{Z} is a 2 by 2 matrix:

$$\mathbf{Z} = \mathbf{E}\mathbf{H}^{-1} \quad (2.5)$$

such that:

$$\begin{bmatrix} Z_{xx} & Z_{xy} \\ Z_{yx} & Z_{yy} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} E_x^{(1)} & E_x^{(2)} \\ E_y^{(1)} & E_y^{(2)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} H_x^{(1)} & H_x^{(2)} \\ H_y^{(1)} & H_y^{(2)} \end{bmatrix}^{-1} \quad (2.6)$$

where 1 and 2 refer to fields associated with plane waves polarized along two perpendicular directions.

Important:

For standard MT data, X = Northing, Y = Easting and Z = Down; which this code uses! Thus:

- Superscript ⁽¹⁾ refers to fields resulting from a plane wave whose electric field is polarized along the Northing direction. And superscript ⁽²⁾ refers to fields resulting from a plane wave whose electric field is polarized along the Easting direction.
 - Z_{xy} is essentially the ratio of the electric field along the Northing and the magnetic field along the Easting.
-

2.2.2 ZTEM Data

The Z-Axis Tipper Electromagnetic Technique (ZTEM) (Lo2008) records the vertical component of the magnetic field everywhere above the survey area while recording the horizontal fields at a ground base reference station. In the same manner as demonstrated for MT, transfer functions are computed which relate the vertical fields to the ground based horizontal fields. This relation is given by:

$$H_z(r) = T_{zx}(r, r_0)H_x(r_0) + T_{zy}(r, r_0)H_y(r_0) \quad (2.7)$$

where r is the location of the vertical field and r_0 is the location of the ground base station. T_{zx} and T_{zy} are the vertical field transfer functions, from z to x and z to y respectively. For a 3-dimensional Earth, the transfer function can be defined using the magnetic field components for 2 orthogonal plane wave polarizations; one polarization with the electric field along the x axis and one polarization with the electric field along the y axis. In this case,

$$\begin{bmatrix} H_z^{(1)} \\ H_z^{(2)} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} H_x^{(1)} & H_y^{(1)} \\ H_x^{(2)} & H_y^{(2)} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} T_{zx} \\ T_{zy} \end{bmatrix} \quad (2.8)$$

where 1 and 2 refer to fields associated with plane waves polarized along two perpendicular directions. Thus the transfer functions are given by:

$$\begin{bmatrix} T_{zx} \\ T_{zy} \end{bmatrix} = (H_x^{(1)}H_y^{(2)} - H_x^{(2)}H_y^{(1)})^{-1} \begin{bmatrix} -H_y^{(1)}H_z^{(2)} + H_y^{(2)}H_z^{(1)} \\ H_x^{(1)}H_z^{(2)} - H_x^{(2)}H_z^{(1)} \end{bmatrix}$$

Important:

For standard natural source data, X = Northing, Y = Easting and Z = Down; which this code uses! Thus:

- Superscript⁽¹⁾ refers to fields resulting from a plane wave whose electric field is polarized along the Northing direction. And superscript⁽²⁾ refers to fields resulting from a plane wave whose electric field is polarized along the Easting direction.
 - T_{zx} is the transfer function related to an incident plane wave whose electric field is polarized along the Northing direction; which produces magnetic fields with components in the Easting direction.
-

2.3 Octree Mesh

By using an Octree discretization of the earth domain, the areas near sources and likely model location can be give a higher resolution while cells grow large at distance. In this manner, the necessary refinement can be obtained without added computational expense. The figure below shows an example of an Octree mesh, with nine cells, eight of which are the base mesh minimum size.

When working with Octree meshes, the underlying mesh is defined as a regular 3D orthogonal grid where the number of cells in each dimension are $2^{n_1} \times 2^{n_2} \times 2^{n_3}$. The cell widths for the underlying mesh are h_1, h_2, h_3 , respectively. This underlying mesh is the finest possible, so that larger cells have side lengths which increase by powers of 2. The idea is that if the recovered model properties change slowly over a certain volume, the cells bounded by this volume can be merged into one without losing the accuracy in modeling, and are only refined when the model begins to change rapidly.

2.4 Discretization of Operators

The operators div , grad , and curl are discretized using a finite volume formulation. Although div and grad do not appear in (2.6), they are required for the solution of the system. The divergence operator is discretized in the usual flux-balance approach, which by Gauss' theorem considers the current flux through each face of a cell. The nodal gradient (operates on a function with values on the nodes) is obtained by differencing adjacent nodes and dividing by edge length. The discretization of the curl operator is computed similarly to the divergence operator by utilizing Stokes theorem by summing the magnetic field components around the edge of each face. Please see [HHG+12] for a detailed description of the discretization process.

2.5 Forward Problem

To solve the forward problem, we must first discretize and solve for the fields in Eq. (2.1), where $e^{-i\omega t}$ is suppressed. Using finite volume discretization, the electric fields on cell edges (\mathbf{u}_e) are obtained by solving the following system at every frequency:

$$[\mathbf{C}^T \mathbf{M}_\mu \mathbf{C} + i\omega \mathbf{M}_\sigma] \mathbf{u}_e = -i\omega \mathbf{s} \quad (2.9)$$

where \mathbf{C} is the curl operator and:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{M}_\mu &= \text{diag}(\mathbf{A}_{f2c}^T \mathbf{V} \boldsymbol{\mu}^{-1}) \\ \mathbf{M}_\sigma &= \text{diag}(\mathbf{A}_{e2c}^T (\mathbf{V} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma})) \end{aligned} \quad (2.10)$$

where \mathbf{V} is a diagonal matrix containing all cell volumes, \mathbf{A}_{f2c} averages from faces to cell centres and \mathbf{A}_{e2c} averages from edges to cell centres. The magnetic permeabilities and conductivities for each cell are contained within vectors $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$, respectively.

The right-hand side \mathbf{s} has values \mathbf{E}_0 on the boundary and 0 at inner edges. Values for \mathbf{E}_0 are obtained by solving a set of 1D problems for a given planewave polarization; either $\mathbf{E}_0 = E_x \hat{x}$ or $\mathbf{E}_0 = E_y \hat{y}$. For explanation of the 1D solution, see Ward and Hohmann.

Once the electric field on cell edges has been computed, we must project to the receivers. For E3DMT version 2, straight wires of finite length are used to measure the average electric field along the path of the wire. And closed wire loops are used to measure the average magnetic field perpendicular to the loop.

Electric field measurements (E) are obtained by integrating the electric field (\mathbf{e}) along the path of the wire to compute the voltage, then dividing by the length of the wire. In practice, electric field measurements can be approximated accurately by applying a linear projection matrix (\mathbf{P}_e) to the electric fields computed on cell edges:

$$E = \frac{1}{|\mathbf{r}_2 - \mathbf{r}_1|} \int_{\mathbf{r}_1}^{\mathbf{r}_2} \mathbf{e} \cdot d\mathbf{l} \approx \mathbf{P}_e \mathbf{u}_e$$

Magnetic field measurements (H) are obtained by integrating the electric field (\mathbf{e}) over the path of close loop to compute the EMF. The EMF is then divided by $i\omega\mu_0 A$, where A is the cross-sectional area, to represent the quantity in terms of the average magnetic field normal to the receiver. In practice, magnetic field measurements can be approximated accurately by applying a linear projection matrix (\mathbf{P}_h) to the electric fields computed on cell edges:

$$H = \frac{1}{i\omega\mu_0 A} \int_C \mathbf{e} \cdot d\mathbf{l} \approx \mathbf{P}_h \mathbf{u}_e$$

To obtain impedance tensor (MT) or ZTEM data, we need the electric and/or magnetic fields for two orthogonal source polarizations; generally one in the x direction and one in the y direction. Let $\mathbf{s}^{(1)}$ and $\mathbf{s}^{(2)}$ denote the right-hand sides for source fields generated for each polarization. And let $\mathbf{u}_e^{(1)}$ and $\mathbf{u}_e^{(2)}$ denote the corresponding solutions for the electric fields on the edges. Then the average electric field (E_x or E_y) or average magnetic field (H_x , H_y or H_z) for some receiver is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} E^{(j)} &= \mathbf{P}_e \mathbf{u}_e^{(j)} = -i\omega \mathbf{P}_e \mathbf{A}(\sigma)^{-1} \mathbf{s}^{(j)} \quad \text{for } j = 1, 2 \\ H^{(j)} &= \mathbf{P}_h \mathbf{u}_e^{(j)} = -i\omega \mathbf{P}_h \mathbf{A}(\sigma)^{-1} \mathbf{s}^{(j)} \quad \text{for } j \in \{1, 2\} \end{aligned} \quad (2.13)$$

where the matrix

$$\mathbf{A}(\sigma) = \mathbf{C}^T \mathbf{M}_\mu \mathbf{C} + i\omega \mathbf{M}_\sigma \quad (2.13)$$

depends on the Earth's conductivity. If the fields at each observation location are known, MT data can be obtained using Eq. (2.6) and ZTEM data can be obtained using Eq. (2.8). The only thing that is needed is the source term for Eq. (2.9).

2.5.1 Source Term

1D Approach

For this approach, we solve a 1D wave equation of the following form:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} \tilde{\mathbf{u}}_e = \tilde{\mathbf{q}} \quad (2.14)$$

where $\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_e$ is the electric field for the 1D solution polarized along the x or y directions. $\tilde{\mathbf{A}}$ is an operator of the form:

$$\tilde{\mathbf{A}} = \mathbf{L} + i\omega\mu_0\tilde{\sigma}$$

such that \mathbf{L} is the Laplacian operator, μ_0 is the permeability of free-space and $\tilde{\sigma}$ is a 1D conductivity model. The right-hand side $\tilde{\mathbf{q}}$ is a vector of zeros except for \tilde{q}_1 . A Dirichlet condition is imposed by setting $A_{11} = 1$ and $\tilde{q}_1 = i\omega\mu_0 h^{-1}$; where h is the layer thickness. Once Eq. (2.14) is solved for a particular frequency, the solution is transferred to the edges of an OcTree mesh. If the electric field is polarized along the x direction, there are no electric fields along y or z; similarly for a solution polarized along the y direction.

Let \mathbf{u}_s and σ_s be the electric fields and 1D conductivity model transferred to the edges of the OcTree mesh, respectively. Then the source term in Eq. (2.9) is computed for a given frequency and polarization using:

$$\frac{1}{i\omega} \mathbf{A} \mathbf{u}_s = \mathbf{s}$$

where \mathbf{A} is similar to expression (2.13), except the mass matrix \mathbf{M}_σ is formed using the transferred conductivity σ_s .

3D Approach

Let σ_b be the 3D background conductivity model. And let \mathbf{A} be an operator similar to expression (2.13), except the mass matrix \mathbf{M}_σ is formed using the background conductivity. If $j = 1, \dots, J$ denotes the indicies for all internal edges and $k = 1, \dots, K$ denotes the indicies for all top edges, then for each polarization we solve a smaller system:

$$\mathbf{A}_{j,j}\mathbf{u}_j = -\mathbf{A}_{j,k}\mathbf{b}$$

where \mathbf{b} is a vector of ones with length K and \mathbf{u}_j is the background electric field on internal edges. From this we form a vector \mathbf{u}_b where:

- $\mathbf{u}_b = 1$ on the top edges
- $\mathbf{u}_b = \mathbf{u}_j$ on internal edges
- $\mathbf{u}_b = 0$ otherwise

Once this is done, the source term in Eq. (2.9) is computed for a given frequency and polarization using:

$$\frac{1}{i\omega}\mathbf{A}\mathbf{u}_s = \mathbf{s}$$

2.6 Sensitivity

2.6.1 MT Data

Impedance tensor data are split into their real and imaginary components. Thus the data at a particular frequency for a particular reading is organized in a vector of the form:

$$\mathbf{Z} = [Z'_{xx}, Z''_{xx}, Z'_{xy}, Z''_{xy}, Z'_{yx}, Z''_{yx}, Z'_{yy}, Z''_{yy}]^T \quad (2.15)$$

where $'$ denotes real components and $''$ denotes imaginary components. To determine the sensitivity of the data (i.e. (2.15)) with respect to the model (σ), we must compute:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{Z}}{\partial \sigma} = \left[\frac{\partial Z'_{xx}}{\partial \sigma}, \frac{\partial Z''_{xx}}{\partial \sigma}, \frac{\partial Z'_{xy}}{\partial \sigma}, \frac{\partial Z''_{xy}}{\partial \sigma}, \frac{\partial Z'_{yx}}{\partial \sigma}, \frac{\partial Z''_{yx}}{\partial \sigma}, \frac{\partial Z'_{yy}}{\partial \sigma}, \frac{\partial Z''_{yy}}{\partial \sigma} \right]^T$$

where the conductivity model σ is real-valued and

$$Z'_{xx} = \text{Re} \left[\frac{E_{xx}H_{yy} - E_{xy}H_{yx}}{H_{xx}H_{yy} - H_{xy}H_{yx}} \right] \quad (2.16)$$

which can be expanded and expressed explicitly in terms of the real and imaginary components of E_{ij} and H_{ij} . Similar expressions result for the other elements of (2.15).

To differentiate (2.16) (or any other element and component of the impedance tensor) with respect to the model, we replace E_{ij} and H_{ij} according to Eq. (2.13) and use the chain rule. The final expression contains the derivative of the electric fields on the edges (\mathbf{u}_e) with respect to the model. This is given by:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}_e}{\partial \sigma} = -i\omega \mathbf{A}^{-1} \text{diag}(\mathbf{u}_e) \mathbf{A}_{e2c}^T \mathbf{V} \quad (2.17)$$

2.6.2 ZTEM Data

ZTEM data are also split into their real and imaginary components. Thus the data at a particular frequency for a particular reading is organized in a vector of the form:

$$\mathbf{T} = [T'_{zx}, T''_{zx}, T'_{zy}, T''_{zy}]^T \quad (2.18)$$

where $'$ denotes real components and $''$ denotes imaginary components. To determine the sensitivity of the data (i.e. (2.18)) with respect to the model (σ), we must compute:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{T}}{\partial \sigma} = \left[\frac{\partial T'_{zx}}{\partial \sigma}, \frac{\partial T''_{zx}}{\partial \sigma}, \frac{\partial T'_{zy}}{\partial \sigma}, \frac{\partial T''_{zy}}{\partial \sigma} \right]^T$$

where the conductivity model σ is real-valued and

$$T'_{zx} = \text{Re} \left[\frac{-H_y^{(1)} H_z^{(2)} + H_y^{(2)} H_z^{(1)}}{H_x^{(1)} H_y^{(2)} - H_x^{(2)} H_y^{(1)}} \right] \quad (2.19)$$

which can be expanded and expressed explicitly in terms of the real and imaginary components of $H_j^{(i)}$. Similar expressions result for the other elements of (2.18).

To differentiate (2.19) (or any other element and component) with respect to the model, we replace $H_j^{(i)}$ according to Eq. (2.13) and use the chain rule. The final expression contains the derivative of the electric fields on the edges (\mathbf{u}_e) with respect to the model with is given by Eq. (2.17).

2.7 Inverse Problem

We are interested in recovering the conductivity distribution for the Earth. However, the numerical stability of the inverse problem is made more challenging by the fact rock conductivities can span many orders of magnitude. To deal with this, we define the model as the log-conductivity for each cell, e.g.:

$$\mathbf{m} = \log(\sigma)$$

The inverse problem is solved by minimizing the following global objective function with respect to the model:

$$\phi(\mathbf{m}) = \phi_d(\mathbf{m}) + \beta \phi_m(\mathbf{m}) \quad (2.20)$$

where ϕ_d is the data misfit, ϕ_m is the model objective function and β is the trade-off parameter. The data misfit ensures the recovered model adequately explains the set of field observations. The model objective function adds geological constraints to the recovered model. The trade-off parameter weights the relative emphasis between fitting the data and imposing geological structures.

2.7.1 Data Misfit

Here, the data misfit is represented as the L2-norm of a weighted residual between the observed data (d_{obs}) and the predicted data for a given conductivity model σ , i.e.:

$$\phi_d = \frac{1}{2} \|\mathbf{W}_d (\mathbf{d}_{obs} - \mathbb{F}[\sigma])\|^2 \quad (2.21)$$

where \mathbf{W}_d is a diagonal matrix containing the reciprocals of the uncertainties ε for each measured data point, i.e.:

$$\mathbf{W}_d = \text{diag}[\varepsilon^{-1}]$$

Important: For a better understanding of the data misfit, see the [GIFtools cookbook](#).

2.7.2 Model Objective Function

Due to the ill-posedness of the problem, there are no stable solutions obtained by freely minimizing the data misfit, and thus regularization is needed. The regularization uses penalties for both smoothness, and likeness to a reference model m_{ref} supplied by the user. The model objective function is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_m = & \frac{\alpha_s}{2} \int_{\Omega} w_s |m - m_{ref}|^2 dV + \frac{\alpha_x}{2} \int_{\Omega} w_x \left| \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (m - m_{ref}) \right|^2 dV \\ & + \frac{\alpha_y}{2} \int_{\Omega} w_y \left| \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (m - m_{ref}) \right|^2 dV + \frac{\alpha_z}{2} \int_{\Omega} w_z \left| \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (m - m_{ref}) \right|^2 dV \end{aligned} \quad (2.22)$$

where $\alpha_s, \alpha_x, \alpha_y$ and α_z weight the relative emphasis on minimizing differences from the reference model and the smoothness along each gradient direction. And w_s, w_x, w_y and w_z are additional user defined weighting functions.

An important consideration comes when discretizing the regularization onto the mesh. The gradient operates on cell centered variables in this instance. Applying a short distance approximation is second order accurate on a domain with uniform cells, but only $\mathcal{O}(1)$ on areas where cells are non-uniform. To rectify this a higher order approximation is used ([HHG+12]). The second order approximation of the model objective function can be expressed as:

$$\phi_m(\mathbf{m}) = (\mathbf{m} - \mathbf{m}_{ref})^T \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{W} (\mathbf{m} - \mathbf{m}_{ref})$$

where the regularizer is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{W} = & \alpha_s \text{diag}(\mathbf{w}_s \odot \mathbf{v}) \\ & + \alpha_x \mathbf{G}_x^T \text{diag}(\mathbf{w}_x \odot \mathbf{v}_x) \\ & + \alpha_y \mathbf{G}_y^T \text{diag}(\mathbf{w}_y \odot \mathbf{v}_y) \\ & + \alpha_z \mathbf{G}_z^T \text{diag}(\mathbf{w}_z \odot \mathbf{v}_z) \end{aligned} \quad (2.22)$$

The Hadamard product is given by \odot , \mathbf{v}_x is the volume of each cell averaged to x-faces, \mathbf{w}_x is the weighting function w_x evaluated on x-faces and \mathbf{G}_x computes the x-component of the gradient from cell centers to cell faces. Similarly for y and z.

If we require that the recovered model values lie between $\mathbf{m}_L \preceq \mathbf{m} \preceq \mathbf{m}_H$, the resulting bounded optimization problem we must solve is:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_m & \phi_d(\mathbf{m}) + \beta \phi_m(\mathbf{m}) \\ \text{s.t.} & \mathbf{m}_L \preceq \mathbf{m} \preceq \mathbf{m}_H \end{aligned} \quad (2.22)$$

A simple Gauss-Newton optimization method is used where the system of equations is solved using ipcg (incomplete preconditioned conjugate gradients) to solve for each G-N step. For more information refer again to [HHG+12] and references therein.

2.7.3 Inversion Parameters and Tolerances

Cooling Schedule

Our goal is to solve Eq. (2.22), i.e.:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_m & \phi_d(\mathbf{m}) + \beta \phi_m(\mathbf{m}) \\ \text{s.t.} & \mathbf{m}_L \preceq \mathbf{m} \preceq \mathbf{m}_H \end{aligned} \quad (2.22)$$

but how do we choose an acceptable trade-off parameter β ? For this, we use a cooling schedule. This is described in the `GIFtools` cookbook. The cooling schedule can be defined using the following parameters:

- **beta_max:** The initial value for β
- **beta_factor:** The factor at which β is decrease to a subsequent solution of Eq. (2.22)
- **nBetas:** The number of times the inversion code will decrease β and solve Eq. (2.22) before it quits
- **Chi Factor:** The inversion program stops when the data misfit $\phi_d \leq N \times Chi\ Factor$, where N is the number of data observations

Gauss-Newton Update

For a given trade-off parameter (β), the model \mathbf{m} is updated using the Gauss-Newton approach. Because the problem is non-linear, several model updates may need to be completed for each β . Where k denotes the Gauss-Newton iteration, we solve:

$$\mathbf{H}_k \delta \mathbf{m}_k = -\nabla \phi_k \quad (2.24)$$

using the current model \mathbf{m}_k and update the model according to:

$$\mathbf{m}_{k+1} = \mathbf{m}_k + \alpha \delta \mathbf{m}_k \quad (2.25)$$

where $\delta \mathbf{m}_k$ is the step direction, $\nabla \phi_k$ is the gradient of the global objective function, \mathbf{H}_k is an approximation of the Hessian and α is a scaling constant. This process is repeated until any of the following occurs:

1. The gradient is sufficiently small, i.e.:

$$\|\nabla \phi_k\|^2 < tol_nl$$

2. The smallest component of the model perturbation its small in absolute value, i.e.:

$$\max(|\delta \mathbf{m}_k|) < mindm$$

3. A max number of GN iterations have been performed, i.e.

$$k = iter_per_beta$$

Gauss-Newton Solve

Here we discuss the details of solving Eq. (2.24) for a particular Gauss-Newton iteration k . Using the data misfit from Eq. (2.21) and the model objective function from Eq. (2.22), we must solve:

$$\left[\mathbf{J}^T \mathbf{W}_d^T \mathbf{W}_d \mathbf{J} + \beta \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{W} \right] \delta \mathbf{m}_k = - \left[\mathbf{J}^T \mathbf{W}_d^T \mathbf{W}_d (\mathbf{d}_{\text{obs}} - \mathbb{F}[\mathbf{m}_k]) + \beta \mathbf{W}^T \mathbf{W} (\mathbf{m}_k - \mathbf{m}_{\text{ref}}) \right] \quad (2.26)$$

where \mathbf{J} is the sensitivity of the data (\mathbf{Z} or \mathbf{T}) to the current model \mathbf{m}_k ; see [sensitivity section](#) to learn how sensitivities are computed. The system is solved for $\delta \mathbf{m}_k$ using the incomplete-preconditioned-conjugate gradient (IPCG) method. This method is iterative and exits with an approximation for $\delta \mathbf{m}_k$. Let i denote an IPCG iteration and let $\delta \mathbf{m}_k^{(i)}$ be the solution to (2.26) at the i^{th} IPCG iteration, then the algorithm quits when:

1. the system is solved to within some tolerance and additional iterations do not result in significant increases in solution accuracy, i.e.:

$$\|\delta \mathbf{m}_k^{(i-1)} - \delta \mathbf{m}_k^{(i)}\|^2 / \|\delta \mathbf{m}_k^{(i-1)}\|^2 < tol_ipcg$$

2. a maximum allowable number of IPCG iterations has been completed, i.e.:

$$i = max_iter_ipcg$$

ELEMENTS OF THE PROGRAM E3DMT

This section provides a brief description of each program in the E3DMT version 1 library. In addition, we describe the file formats for all input and supporting files used by the coding library.

3.1 Executables

Important: Although described here, this generation of the code may not be supported by GIFtools in the future.

The main executable programs within the E3DMT version 1 program library are:

- **e3dmt_fwd:** Solves the forward problem. Computes the electric and magnetic response to a 3D conductivity model (fields, and impedance)
- **e3dmt:** Solves the inverse problem using a direct solver approach (MUMPS). Recovers a conductivity model by inverting MT or ZTEM data. All entries of the impedance tensor or transfer function are needed.
- **e3dmt_iter:** Solves the inverse problem using an iterative solver approach. Recovers a conductivity model by inverting MT or ZTEM data. All entries of the impedance tensor or transfer function are needed.
- **create_octree_mesh_e3dmt:** Creates an octree mesh based on the *survey file*

Common Octree utility programs used with this package include:

- **blk3cell:** Creates models from a set of blocks on a tensor mesh
- **3DModel2Octree:** Converts models from tensor to Octree meshes
- **interface_weights:** Creates interface weights

3.2 Main Input Files

Here, we describe the main input files for executables contained with the E3DMT version 1 package.

3.2.1 Create OcTree Mesh Input File

OcTree meshes used in the E3DMT code are created using the program `create_octree_mesh_e3dmt.exe`. Parameters necessary for defining the OcTree mesh are set in the input file. The lines within the input file are as follows:

Line #	Parameter	Descriptions
1	<i>dx dy dz</i>	min. cell widths in x, y and z for base mesh
2	<i>x_pad y_pad down_pad up_pad</i>	sets the extend of mesh in x, y and z direction
3	<i>dist_1 dist_2 dist_3</i>	sets cell sizes within core mesh region
4	<i>n1 n2 n3</i>	sets thickness of cells of finest discretization near receivers
5	<i>locFile</i>	the file containing observation locations
6	<i>topoFile</i>	sets topography
7	<i>shift_data</i>	<i>description needed. leave as NOT_SHIFT_DATA</i>
8	<i>interp_topo</i>	sets level of discretization for surface topography
9	<i>start_point</i>	sets the starting point for the mesh generation

```

200 200 100          ! min dx
5000 5000 5000 5000 ! padding x, y, down, air
1600 800 800       ! depths for area of interest
4 4 4             ! # of small cells around receivers
ONLY_LOC input_files\dataPoints.txt ! Survey (data locations) file
TOPO_CONST 0      ! topo file | TOPO_CONST val
NOT_SHIFT_DATA    ! SHIFT_DATA | NOT_SHIFT_DATA
APPROXTOPO        ! APPROXTOPO | GOODTOPO
START_LARGE_CELLS ! START_LARGE_CELLS | START_SMALL_CELLS
1,1               All

```

Fig. 3.1: Example input file for creating octree mesh ([Download](#))

Line Descriptions

- **dx dy dz:** Minimum cell widths in x, y and z for the base mesh.
- **x_pad y_pad down_pad up_pad:** Distance from the origin in the x, y, downward and upward directions, respectively, that the mesh extends.

Important: In the case where you are modeling ZTEM data and the base station is very far from the general survey region, you **MUST** ensure the padding extends far enough to contain the base station. Otherwise, the mesh generation will fail.

- **dist_1 dist_2 dist_3:** Sets the distance from surface topography and receivers in which the cells widths are increased by a factor of 2 in x, y and z. Up to a depth of *dist_1* from surface topography and within a horizontal distance of *dist_1* from any receiver, the smallest cell size is used (set by *dx*, *dy*, *dz*). For the following *dist_2* metres, the cell widths are doubled. For the following *dist_3* metres, the cell widths are doubled again. Outside a depth and horizontal distance of $h1+h2+h3$, the cells widths increase by a factor of 2 for every additional layer (see the figure below).

- **n1 n2 n3:** This sets the thicknesses of layers of finest discretization near the receivers. **n1 = 4** means that around each receiver, there is a layer 4 cells thick that uses the finest discretization. This is followed by a layer which is **n2** cells thick, where the cell dimensions are increased by a factor of 2. Likewise for the 3rd layer.
- **locFile:** Contains the locations of the receivers. The user may either enter the file path to an *observed data* file, or the flag “ONLY_LOC” followed by the path to a *data points* file.
- **topoFile:** If a topography file is available, the file path to the topography file is entered; see *topography file* for format. In the case of flat topography, the user instead enter “TOPO_CONST”, followed by a space, then the elevation of the surface topography; for example “TOPO_CONST 125.5”.
- **shift_data:** Here, there are 3 options:
 - If the flag “NOT_SHIFT_DATA” is used, then it is possible for stations to lie below the topography specified on line 6.
 - If “SHIFT_TO_SURFACE *filename*” is used, then a locations file is created in which all stations are projected to be at the discretized surface topography. This is used primarily for MT surveys
 - If “SHIFT_FLIGHT_HEIGHT *filename*” is used, then a locations file is created in which the data locations are shifted to preserve true flight height over the discretized surface topography. This is used for ZTEM surveys.
- **interp_topo:** Set as either “APPROXTOPO” or “GOODTOPO”. If “APPROXTOPO” is chosen, there will only be fine cells close to the survey, whereas “GOODTOPO” will place fine cells everywhere on the surface.
- **start_point:** Set as either “START_LARGE_CELLS” or “START_SMALL_CELLS”. This line sets the starting point for the mesh generation. Starting the mesh population from large cells greatly reduces initial memory required and is therefore suggested. Large cells are divided in this algorithm to produce the OcTree mesh.

Approximate versus Good Topography

Below, we see the difference between entering “APPROXTOPO” (top) and “GOODTOPO” (bottom) into *interp_top*. For “APPROXTOPO”, the mesh ultimately contains a smaller total number of cells, as discretization near the surface is coarser. For “GOODTOPO”, the mesh contains a larger total number of cells because the surface topography is discretized to the finest cell size.

3.2.2 Create Model Input File

Input File and Line Descriptions for blk3cell

The input file defines the properties of the model (conductivity/susceptibility/active) created using **blk3cell.exe**. The user specifies the locations, dimensions and values for a set of blocks. All undefined cells within the mesh are set to the background value. The format for this file is as follows:

Line #	Parameter	Description
1	σ_b	background conductivity/susceptibility
2	N	number of blocks
3	$x_1^{(1)} x_2^{(1)} y_1^{(1)} y_2^{(1)} z_{top}^{(1)} z_{bottom}^{(1)} m^{(1)}$	Block 1
4	$x_1^{(2)} x_2^{(2)} y_1^{(2)} y_2^{(2)} z_{top}^{(2)} z_{bottom}^{(2)} m^{(2)}$	Block 2
⋮	⋮	⋮
	$x_1^{(N)} x_2^{(N)} y_1^{(N)} y_2^{(N)} z_{top}^{(N)} z_{bottom}^{(N)} m^{(N)}$	Block 3

where superscript (i) for $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$ refers to a particular block. $x_1, x_2, y_1, y_2, z_{top}$ and z_{bottom} define the dimensions of each block and m defines conductivity/susceptibility value. An example is shown below.


```
blk3cell.inp (~\Documents\Repos...mt\assets\input_files_ver1) - GVIM
File Edit Tools Syntax Buffers Window Help
[Icons]
0.01  ! background
3      ! number of blocks
3400  4600  1600  4600  -400  -1200  1.
1600  4600  3400  4600  -400  -1200  1.
-999999 999999 -999999 999999 999999 0 1.e-8
1,1 All
```

Fig. 3.2: Example input file for blk3cell (Download)

Input File and Line Descriptions for Model2Octree

The file **3DModel2Octree.inp** contains the paths to the tensor mesh (**3D_mesh.txt**), tensor model (**3Dmodel.con**) and octree mesh (**octree_mesh.txt**) as well as other necessary parameters. The format of the input file is as follows:

Line #	Parameter	Description
1	<i>Model Type</i>	Either <i>LIN_MODEL</i> or <i>LOG_MODEL</i>
2	<i>Octree mesh</i>	File path to Octree mesh
3	<i>Tensor mesh</i>	File path to tensor mesh
4	<i>Tensor model</i>	3D model on tensor mesh
5	<i>Output mesh name</i>	Name for re-meshed Octree mesh or enter <i>USE_INPUT_MESH</i>
6	<i>Output model name</i>	File name for conductivity model on Octree mesh
7	<i>Start point</i>	Either <i>START_LARGE_CELLS</i> or <i>START_SMALL_CELLS</i>

Note:

Consider the following with regards to line 5:

- The edges of structures defined within the underlying tensor mesh may bisect larger cells within the Octree mesh. If an output name is provided, the program will output a new Octree mesh with refined cells such that the edges of structures do not bisect cells. Thus the input and output Octree mesh may have a different number of cells.
- If *USE_INPUT_MESH* is entered, the model on the underlying tensor mesh is interpolated onto the pre-existing Octree mesh.

An example input file and the resulting conductivity model on the octree mesh are shown below

```

LOG_MODEL          ? LOG_MODEL | LIN_MODEL
input_files\octree_mesh.txt    ? input octree mesh file
input_files\3D_mesh.txt       ? input 3D mesh
output_files\3Dmodel.con      ? input 3D model
USE_INPUT_MESH              ? output octree mesh file
octree_model.con             ? output octree model file
START_LARGE_CELLS           ? START_LARGE_CELLS | START_SMALL_CELLS
                             1,1                All

```

Fig. 3.3: Example input file for 3DModel2Octree.exe ([Download](#))

3.2.3 Forward Modeling Input File

The forward problem is solved using the executable program `e3dmt_fwd.exe`. Parameters necessary for running the forward modeling code are set in the input file. The lines of input file are as follows:

Line #	Parameter	Description
1	<i>OcTree Mesh</i>	path to octree mesh file
2	<i>Receiver Locations</i>	path to observation locations file
3	<i>Real Conductivity</i>	path to conductivity model
4	<i>Imaginary Conductivity</i>	path to imaginary conductivity file (optional)
5	<i>1D Background Conductivity</i>	set 1D conductivity model
6	<i>Background Susceptibility</i>	set background susceptibility
7	<i>Topography</i>	set topography

```
e3dmt_fwd.inp (~\Documents\Repositories\e3dmt\assets\input_files_ver1) - GVIM
File Edit Tools Syntax Buffers Window Help
input_files/octree_mesh.txt      ! octree mesh file
input_files/dataPoints.txt      ! locations file
input_files/octree_model.con    ! real conductivity model | VALUE
NO_IMAG_COND                    ! imaginary conductivity model | NO_IMAG_COND
VALUE 0.01                      ! 1D background conductivity file | VALUE #
NO_SUS                          ! background susceptibility model | NO_SUS
input_files/active_cells_topo.txt ! topography active cell file | ALL_ACTIVE
                                1,1
                                All
```

Fig. 3.4: Example input file for forward modeling program ([Download](#)).

Line Descriptions

- **OcTree Mesh:** file path to the OcTree mesh file
- **Receiver Locations:** file path to the *survey file*.
- **Real Conductivity:** file path to the conductivity model. If complex conductivities are being used, this model represents real-valued conductivities.
- **Imaginary Conductivity:** If the conductivity model used in the forward simulation is strictly real-valued, the user may enter “NO_IMAG_COND” on this line. Otherwise, the user enters the file path to the imaginary conductivity model.
- **1D Background Conductivity:** The user may supply the file path to a [1D background conductivity model](#) . If a homogeneous background conductivity is being used, the user enters “VALUE” followed by a space and a numerical value; example “VALUE 0.01”

Important:

- The number of layers in the 1D model for E3DMT must equal the number of underlying mesh cells in the vertical direction. Thus if underlying mesh for the OcTree mesh is 1028 by 1028 by 512, the 1D model must have 512 layer conductivities.
- The boundary conditions computed using 1D models is only accurate when surface topography is minimal. In the case where surface topography is significant, it is suggested the user used E3DMT version 2.

- **Background Susceptibility:** The user may provide the file path to a background susceptibility model on this line. If a constant susceptibility is being used, “VALUE” may be entered and followed by the background susceptibility. For no background susceptibility, the flag “NO_SUS” is used.
- **Topography:** The user may supply the file path to an active cells model file or type “ALL_ACTIVE”. The active cells model has values 1 for cells lying below the surface topography and values 0 for cells lying above.

3.2.4 Face Weights Input File

The parameters used to create the interface weights are defined in the input file. The lines within the input file are as follows:

Line #	Parameter	Description
1	<i>OcTree Mesh</i>	path to octree mesh
2	<i>Active Cells</i>	path to active cells model
3	<i>Conductivity Model</i>	path to conductivity model
4	<i>Mapping Type</i>	set as log or linear mapping
5	<i>Gradient Tolerance</i>	set threshold for largest gradients preserved in recovered model
6	<i># Surface Layers</i>	set number of cells below surface in which weighting horizontal smoothing is applied
7	<i>Horizontal Surface Weights</i>	sets the weighting for horizontal smoothing for each layer
8	<i>Output Name</i>	name for output face weighting file

```

interface_weights.inp (~\Documents\MATLAB\E3DMT_practice\face_model) - GVIM
File Edit Tools Syntax Buffers Window Help
octree_mesh.txt      ! octree mesh file path
active_cells_topo.txt ! active cells model path | ALL_ACTIVE
reference_mod.con    ! model file path | NO_MODEL
LOG_MODEL            ! LIN_MODEL | LOG_MODEL
1e-4 1e-3            ! min_val max_val (gradient tolerances)
2                    ! # of surface layers
100 50               ! w_x w_y (surface weight values for X and Y interfaces)
octree_interface.txt ! output interface weights file name
1,1                  All

```

Fig. 3.5: Example input file for creating interface weights.

Line Descriptions

- **OcTree Mesh:** file path to the OcTree mesh file
- **Active Topography Cells:** Here, the user can choose to specify the cells which lie below the surface topography. To do this, the user may supply the file path to an active cells model file or type “ALL_ACTIVE”. The active cells model has values 1 for cells lying below the surface topography and values 0 for cells lying above.
- **Conductivity Model:** Here, the user provides reference model containing the conductivity structures they would like to preserve. The flag “NO_MODEL” may be used if only surface weighting is applied.
- **Mapping Type:** Here, the user specifies whether the mapping between the model value and the physical property value on the mesh is linear or logarithmic. To specify, use the flags “LIN_MODEL” or “LOG_MODEL”. In the case of E3DMT, the inversion recovers the log-conductivity. As a result, the user should use “LOG_MODEL”.

- **Gradient Tolerance:** Here, the user specifies the threshold for the largest gradients that can be preserved followed by a replacement value if the gradient is over the threshold (i.e. *Val1 Val2*). If we try to preserve very large gradients due to blocky models, we may fit these features at the expense of others. The tolerance threshold and replacement value should be determined from the expected physical property values and cell size. For *log-conductivity and 100m cell widths, a good threshold might be: σ_{max}/dh* .
- **# Surface Layers:** This represents the first parameter used to apply surface weighting. Here, the user specifies how many cell layers below the surface will have surface weighting in X and Y.
- **Horizontal Surface Weights:** Here, the user specifies the weights on X and Y faces for every layer (from surface layer downwards). Essentially, we are invoking a smoothness along the X and Y directions that decreases with depth. The user must enter a set of decreasing values separated by spaces. The number of values that must be entered is equal to the integer value set on the previous line.
- **Output Name:** File name for the output interface weights file.

3.2.5 Inversion Input File

Both `e3dmt.exe` and `e3dmt_iter.exe` use the same input file. The lines of input file are as follows:

Line #	Description	Description
1	<i>OcTree Mesh</i>	path to octree mesh file
2	<i>Observation File</i>	path to observations file
3	<i>1D Background Conductivity</i>	1D background conductivity model
4	<i>Initial Model</i>	initial model
5	<i>Reference Model</i>	reference model
6	<i>Background Susceptibility Model</i>	background susceptibility model
7	<i>Active Topography Cells</i>	topography
8	<i>Active Model Cells</i>	active model cells
9	<i>Cell Weights</i>	additional cell weights
10	<i>Face Weights</i>	additional face weights
11	<i>beta_max beta_min beta_factor</i>	cooling schedule for beta parameter
12	<i>alpha_s alpha_x alpha_y alpha_z</i>	weighting constants for smallness and smoothness constraints
13	<i>Chi Factor</i>	stopping criteria for inversion
14	<i>tol_nl mindm iter_per_beta</i>	set the number of Gauss-Newton iteration for each beta value
15	<i>tol_ipcg max_iter_ipcg</i>	set the tolerance and number of iterations for Gauss-Newton solve
16	<i>Reference Model Update</i>	reference model
17	<i>Hard Constraints</i>	use <i>SMOOTH_MOD</i> or <i>SMOOTH_MOD_DIFF</i>
18	<i>Bounds</i>	upper and lower bounds for recovered model
19	<i>BICG Parameters (Iterative .exe only)</i>	set solver parameters for iterative inversion

```

input_files/octree_mesh.txt      ! mesh file
input_files/MT_data.dat         ! data file
VALUE 0.01                      ! 1d background
VALUE 0.01                      ! initial model
VALUE 0.01                      ! reference model
NO_SUS                          ! background susceptibility model | NO_SUS
input_files/active_cells_topo.txt ! topography active cell file | ALL_ACTIVE
ALL_ACTIVE                      ! model active cell file | ALL_ACTIVE
NO_WEIGHT                       ! cell weight file | NO_WEIGHT | ERBLOM
NO_FACE_WEIGHT                 ! face weighting file | NO_FACE_WEIGHT
0.1 1e-6 0.2                   ! DEFAULT ! beta_max beta_min beta_factor
2.5e-5 1 1 0.25                ! alpha_s alpha_x alpha_y alpha_z
0.6                             ! chifact
1.e-2 1.e-3 3                  ! tol_n1 mindm iter_per_beta
1.e-2 20                        ! tol_ipcg max_iter_ipcg
NOT_CHANGE_MREF                ! CHANGE_MREF | NOT_CHANGE_MREF
SMOOTH_MOD_DIF                 ! SMOOTH_MOD | SMOOTH_MOD_DIF
BOUNDS_NONE                    ! BOUNDS_CONST 1.e-10 1.e+10 ! BOUNDS_NONE
1e-11 1e-5 150 1e6            ! tol_bicg tol_ipcg_bicg max_it_bicg freq_Aphi (iterative only)
                                     1,1      All

```

Fig. 3.6: Example input file for the inversion program ([Download](#)).

Line Descriptions

- **OcTree Mesh:** file path to the OcTree mesh file
- **Observation File:** file path to the *observed data file*
- **1D Background Conductivity:** The user may supply the file path to a [1D background conductivity model](#) , or if a homogeneous background conductivity is being used, the user may enter “VALUE” followed by a space and a numerical value (example “VALUE 0.01”). The way the 1D model is used to determine the boundary conditions for solving the full 3D problem depends on the active topography cells options on [line 7](#). Before continuing, the user is urged to read the section on [boundary conditions](#).

Important:

- The number of layers in the 1D model for E3DMT must equal the number of underlying mesh cells in the vertical direction. Thus if underlying mesh for the OcTree mesh is 1028 by 1028 by 512, the 1D model must have 512 layer conductivities.
- The boundary conditions computed using 1D models is only accurate when surface topography is minimal. In the case where surface topography is significant, it is suggested the user used E3DMT version 2.

- **Initial Model:** The user may supply the file path to an initial conductivity model. If a homogeneous conductivity value is being used for all active cells, the user can enter “VALUE” followed by a space and a numerical value; example “VALUE 0.01”.
- **Reference Model:** The user may supply the file path to a reference conductivity model. If a homogeneous conductivity value is being used for all active cells, the user can enter “VALUE” followed by a space and a numerical value; example “VALUE 0.01”.
- **Reference Susceptibility Model:** The user may supply the file path to a background susceptibility model. If the Earth is non-magnetic, the user may use the flag “NO_SUS”.
- **Active Topography Cells:** Here, the user can choose to specify the cells which lie below the surface topography. To do this, the user may supply the file path to an active cells model file or type “ALL_ACTIVE”. The active cells model has values 1 for cells lying below the surface topography and values 0 for cells lying above.

- **Active Model Cells:** Here, the user can choose to specify the model cells which are active during the inversion. To do this, the user may supply the file path to an active cells model file or type “ALL_ACTIVE”. The active cells model has values 1 for cells lying below the surface topography and values 0 for cells lying above. Values for inactive cells are provided by the background conductivity model.
- **Cell Weights:** Here, the user specifies whether cell weights are supplied. If so, the user provides the file path to a *cell weights file*. If no additional cell weights are supplied, the user enters “NO_WEIGHT”.
- **Face Weights:** Here, the user specifies whether face weights are supplied. If so, the user provides the file path to a face weights file *cell weights file*. If no additional cell weights are supplied, the user enters “NO_FACE_WEIGHT”. The user may also enter “EKBL0M” for 1-norm approximation to recover sharper edges.
- **beta_max beta_min beta_factor:** Here, the user specifies protocols for the trade-off parameter (beta). *beta_max* is the initial value of beta, *beta_min* is the minimum allowable beta the program can use before quitting and *beta_factor* defines the factor by which beta is decreased at each iteration; example “1E4 10 0.2”. The user may also enter “DEFAULT” if they wish to have beta calculated automatically. See theory section for *cooling schedule*.
- **alpha_s alpha_x alpha_y alpha_z: Alpha parameters .** Here, the user specifies the relative weighting between the smallness and smoothness component penalties on the recovered models.
- **Chi Factor:** The chi factor defines the target misfit for the inversion. A chi factor of 1 means the target misfit is equal to the total number of data observations. For more, see the [GIFtools cookbook](#) .
- **tol_nl mindm iter_per_beta:** Here, the user specifies the number of Newton iterations. *tol_nl* is the Newton iteration tolerance (how close the gradient is to zero), *mindm* is the minimum model perturbation δm allowed and *iter_per_beta* is the number of iterations per beta value. See theory section for *cooling schedule* and *Gauss-Newton update*.
- **tol_ipcg max_iter_ipcg:** Here, the user specifies solver parameters. *tol_ipcg* defines how well the iterative solver does when solving for δm and *max_iter_ipcg* is the maximum iterations of incomplete-preconditioned-conjugate gradient. See theory on *Gauss-Newton solve*.
- **Reference Model Update:** Here, the user specifies whether the reference model is updated at each inversion step result. If so, enter “CHANGE_MREF”. If not, enter “NOT_CHANGE_MREF”.
- **Hard Constraints:** SMOOTH_MOD runs the inversion without implementing a reference model (essential $m_{ref} = 0$). “SMOOTH_MOD_DIF” constrains the inversion in the smallness and smoothness terms using a reference model.
- **Bounds:** Bound constraints on the recovered model. Choose “BOUNDS_CONST” and enter the values of the minimum and maximum model conductivity; example “BOUNDS_CONST 1E-6 0.1”. Enter “BOUNDS_NONE” if the inversion is unbounded, or if there is no a-prior information about the subsurface model.
- **BICG Parameters (omit line if using direct solver):** In order, the user specifies values for *tol_bicg*, *tol_ipcg_bicg*, *max_it_bicg* and *freq_Aphi*; Example: *1E-10 1E-5 100 -1*. These parameters are defined as follows:
 - **tol_bicg:** relative tolerance (stopping criteria) when solver is used during forward modeling; i.e. solves Eq. (2.9). Ideally, this number is very small (default = 1e-10).
 - **tol_ipcg_bicg:** relative tolerance (stopping criteria) when solver needed in computation of δm during Gauss Newton iteration; i.e. must solve Eq. (2.17) to solve Eq. (2.24). This value does not need to be as large as the previous parameter (default = 1e-5).
 - **max_it_bicg:** maximum number of BICG iterations (default = 100)
 - **freq_Aphi:** for frequencies below *freq_Aphi*, an SSOR preconditioner is constructed and used to solve the system more efficiently. However, the construction of preconditioners at each frequency may required a sig-

nificant portion of additional RAM. To solve the system for all frequencies without using a preconditioner, set this value to a negative number (default = -1).

Details regarding boundary conditions

The way the 1D model is used to determine the boundary conditions for the full 3D problem depends on *background conductivity* (line 3) and the *active topography cells* (line 7). This can be explained as follows:

- Assume *VALUE* is used to define the 1D background model (line 3) and the flag *ALL_ACTIVE* is used to define active topography cells (line 7). Then the boundary conditions are obtained by solving the fields for a whole space. This approach is strongly discouraged!
- Assume *VALUE* is used to define the 1D background model (line 3) and an *active cells model* is used to define the active topography cells (line 7). Then the highest surface elevation in the active cells model is used as the surface elevation for the 1D model. Below this surface, the background conductivity is equal to the specified value. Above this surface, the background conductivity is set to air.
- Assume a *1D model* defines the background conductivity (line 3) and the flag *ALL_ACTIVE* is used to define active topography cells (line 7). The top of the 1D model corresponds to the top of the OcTree mesh when solving the 1D problem. As a result, it is important to include air cells in the 1D model.
- Assume a *1D model* defines the background conductivity (line 3) and an *active cells model* is used to define the active topography cells (line 7). Then the highest surface elevation in the active cells model is used as the surface elevation for the 1D model. The 1D problem is still solved and the top of the 1D model still corresponds to the top of the OcTree mesh. However, all layers above the surface are set to air regardless of the values specified in the 1D model.

3.3 Supporting Files

Here, we describe the formats of supporting files used to run E3DMT executable files. The input files for each executable program are described in the *running the programs* section.

3.3.1 Survey and Locations File

The survey and locations file is used to predict synthetic field data (forward modeling) using the E3DMT version 1 code. This file contains all necessary survey information including: the number of transmitters (groups of natural source data), data types, measurement frequencies and receiver locations.

Note:

- Bolded entries are fixed flags recognized by the Fortran codes and blue hyperlinked entries are values/regular expressions specified by the user
 - Each unique data type, frequency and set of observation locations corresponds to a unique “transmitter”; e.g. 2 transmitters must be specified if the same data are collected at the same locations at 2 different frequencies.
 - Each block containing DATATYPE, FREQUENCY, N_RECV and the data array
-

The lines of a locations file with one or more transmitters is formatted as follows:

N_TRX [A](#)

DATATYPE *B*
FREQUENCY *C*
N_RECV *D*
Data Array

DATATYPE *B*
FREQUENCY *C*
N_RECV *D*
Data Array

⋮

DATATYPE *B*
FREQUENCY *C*
N_RECV *D*
Data Array

```

dataPoints.txt - Notepad
File Edit Format View Help
N_TRX 4
!IGNORE -0
DATATYPE MTZ
FREQUENCY 1.000000E+002 ! frequenc
N_RECV 900 ! # of Receivers
2.500000E+002 2.500000E+002 0.000000E+000
2.500000E+002 7.500000E+002 0.000000E+000
2.500000E+002 1.250000E+003 0.000000E+000
2.500000E+002 1.750000E+003 0.000000E+000
2.500000E+002 2.250000E+003 0.000000E+000
2.500000E+002 2.750000E+003 0.000000E+000
2.500000E+002 3.250000E+003 0.000000E+000
2.500000E+002 3.750000E+003 0.000000E+000
2.500000E+002 4.250000E+003 0.000000E+000
2.500000E+002 4.750000E+003 0.000000E+000
2.500000E+002 5.250000E+003 0.000000E+000
2.500000E+002 5.750000E+003 0.000000E+000
2.500000E+002 6.250000E+003 0.000000E+000
2.500000E+002 6.750000E+003 0.000000E+000
2.500000E+002 7.250000E+003 0.000000E+000
2.500000E+002 7.750000E+003 0.000000E+000

```

Fig. 3.7: Example locations file for MTZ data.

Parameter Descriptions

- **(A) Number of transmitters:** In line 1, the number of transmitters/groups of natural source EM data is specified. Example: *N_TRX 3*
- **(B) Data type:** For the data corresponding to each transmitter, this line sets the type of data. Example: *DATATYPE MTZ*. There are 4 options for DATATYPE:
 - “MTZ” - MT data (Both real and imaginary impedance tensor data)
 - “MTT” - ZTEM data (Hx and Hy constant at first receiver location and first receiver station defines base station)
 - “MTE” - ZTEM data where Hx, Hy are calculated at the base station from the initial model
 - “MTH” - ZTEM data (reference is at the data points - no base station)

Important:

- Data type MTE cannot be used in forward modeling, as there is no initial model initial model in this case.
- When modeling MT and ZTEM data simultaneously, you must choose either type MTZ and MTT OR MTZ and MTH; e.g. you cannot have MTT and MTH in the same locations file.

- **(C) Frequency:** Frequency at which the corresponding set of field observations are made. Example: *FREQUENCY 1.0000E+002*.
- **(D) Number of receivers:** Number of receivers collecting data at the aforementioned frequency for the aforementioned data type. Example: *N_RECV 900*.
- **Data Array:** Contains the locations and field observations for the data specified by *data type*. The number of lines in this array is equal to the number of receivers. The number of columns depends on the type of data specified. The columns for defined for each array are show *below*.

Data Array**MT data (DATATYPE = MTZ or MTE) or ZTEM data:**

No matter what data type is being used (DATATYPE = MTZ, MTE, MTT or MTH), each row of the data array contains the x, y and z positions for readings at a particular location, i.e.:

| *Easting* | *Northing* | *Elevation* |

Important:

- The locations are Easting, Northing and elevation in metres.
- If MT and/or ZTEM data are being modeled, the frequencies do not need to match nor do the locations for each frequency.
- For **MTT data (ZTEM)**, the first line in the array refers to the base/reference station location. Thus if there are N receiver locations specified for a given array with data type “MTT”, the forward model will output $N - 1$ rows of predicted data.
- For **MTH data (ZTEM)**, measurements Hx, Hy and Hz are taken at the same location. Thus if there are N receiver locations specified for a given array with data type “MTH”, the forward model will output N rows of predicted data.

3.3.2 Predicted Data File

The predicted data file is output from **e3dMTfwd.exe** and contains the locations and predicted data. The order of the data point is in the same order as the *survey and locations file*. Each block, separated by a blank line, are the data for a particular transmitter and frequency. Thus predicted data files take the format:

Data Array 1

Data Array 2

⋮

Data Array N

MT data (DATATYPE = MTZ)

Each row in the array contains the elements of the impedance tensor at a particular location separated into real and imaginary components. The units for predicted MT data are (V/A). The columns for this data format are as follows:

$$| \textit{Easting} | \textit{Northing} | \textit{Elevation} | Z'_{xx} | Z''_{xx} | Z'_{xy} | Z''_{xy} | Z'_{yx} | Z''_{yx} | Z'_{yy} | Z''_{yy} |$$

where

- The data location is given by Easting, Northing and Elevation in metres
- Z'_{ij} is the real component of entry i,j of the impedance tensor
- Z''_{ij} is the imaginary component of entry i,j of the impedance tensor

Important: For standard MT data, X = Northing, Y = Easting and Z = Down; which this code uses! Thus Z_{xy} is essentially the ratio of the electric field along the Northing and the magnetic field along the Easting. For more, see the [theory section](#).

ZTEM data (DATATYPE = MTT, MTE or MTH)

Each row in the array contains the elements of the transfer function at a particular location separated into real and imaginary components. Predicted ZTEM data are unitless with no normalization factor. The columns for this data format are as follows:

$$| \textit{Easting} | \textit{Northing} | \textit{Elevation} | T'_{zx} | T''_{zx} | T'_{zy} | T''_{zy} |$$

where

- The data location is given by Easting, Northing and Elevation in metres
- T'_{zx} is the real component of T_{zx}
- T''_{zx} is the imaginary component of T_{zx}

and similarly for y .

Important: For standard natural source data, X = Northing, Y = Easting and Z = Down; which this code uses! Thus T_{zx} is the transfer function related to an incident plane wave whose electric field is polarized along the Northing direction; which produces magnetic fields with components in the Easting direction. For more, see the [theory section](#).

3.3.3 Observations File

This file is input when inverting field-collected data. This file contains the survey information, field observations and data uncertainties.

Important: As of May 2018, the user must invert all 4 components of the impedance tensor for MT data OR both components of the transfer function for ZTEM data. Also, flags cannot be used to omit data points.

Format

Note:

- Bolded entries are fixed flags recognized by the Fortran codes and blue hyperlinked entries are values/regular expressions specified by the user
 - Each unique data type, frequency and set of observation locations corresponds to a unique “transmitter”; e.g. 2 transmitters must be specified if the same data are collected at the same locations at 2 different frequencies.
 - Each block contains DATATYPE, FREQUENCY, N_RECV and the data array
-

The lines of a data file with one or more transmitters are formatted as follows:

N_TRX *A*
!IGNORE *B*

DATATYPE *C*
FREQUENCY *D*
N_RECV *E*
Data Array

DATATYPE *C*
FREQUENCY *D*
N_RECV *E*
Data Array

⋮

DATATYPE *C*
FREQUENCY *D*
N_RECV *E*
Data Array

```

MTdataFile.txt
N_TRX 4
!IGNORE -0

DATATYPE MTZ
FREQUENCY 1.000000E+002      ! frequency
N_RECV 900      ! # of receivers
2.500000E+002  2.500000E+002  0.000000E+000  -2.009349E-005  3.941896E-005  -4.449435E-006  3.359877E-005  1.959
2.500000E+002  7.500000E+002  0.000000E+000  -2.020319E-005  3.942445E-005  -2.709045E-006  3.351175E-005  1.960
2.500000E+002  1.250000E+003  0.000000E+000  -1.986017E-005  3.940730E-005  -8.264591E-007  3.341762E-005  1.961
2.500000E+002  1.750000E+003  0.000000E+000  -1.901546E-005  3.936506E-005  1.268664E-006  3.343973E-005  1.962
2.500000E+002  2.250000E+003  0.000000E+000  -1.757231E-005  3.929290E-005  3.690022E-006  3.356080E-005  1.962
2.500000E+002  2.750000E+003  0.000000E+000  -1.534245E-005  3.918141E-005  6.578233E-006  3.370521E-005  1.963
2.500000E+002  3.250000E+003  0.000000E+000  -1.199707E-005  3.901414E-005  1.004256E-005  3.387842E-005  1.963

```

Fig. 3.8: Example data file for MTZ data.

Parameter Descriptions

- **(A) Number of transmitters:** In line 1, the number of transmitters/groups of natural source EM data is specified. Example: *N_TRX 3*
- **(B) Flag to ignore data entries:** A regular expression is entered, signifying data in the data structure which is ignored during the inversion. Example: *!IGNORE -0*
- **(C) Data type:** For the data corresponding to each transmitter, this line sets the type of data. Example: *DATATYPE MTZ*. There are 4 options for *DATATYPE*:
 - “MTZ” - MT data (Both real and imaginary impedance tensor data)
 - “MTT” - ZTEM data (Hx and Hy constant at first receiver location and first receiver station defines base station)
 - “MTE” - ZTEM data where Hx, Hy are calculated at the base station from the initial model
 - “MTH” - ZTEM data (reference is at the data points - no base station)

Important:

- When modeling MT and ZTEM data simultaneously, you must choose either type MTZ and MTT or MT and MTE or MTZ and MTH; e.g. you cannot have MTT, MTE and MTH in the same observations file.
-
- **(D) Frequency:** Frequency at which the corresponding set of field observations are made. Example: *FREQUENCY 1.0000E+002*.
 - **(E) Number of receivers:** Number of receivers collecting data at the aforementioned frequency for the aforementioned data type. Example: *N_RECV 900*.
 - **Data Array:** Contains the locations and field observations for the data specified by *data type*. The number of lines in this array is equal to the number of receivers. The number of columns depends on the type of data specified. The columns for defined for each array are show *below*.

Data Arrays by Type

MT data (DATATYPE = MTZ):

Each row in the array contains the elements of the impedance tensor at a particular location separated into real and imaginary components, along with the corresponding uncertainties. The units for MT data are (V/A). [Download MT data example](#) . The columns for this data format are as follows:

$$| \textit{Easting} | \textit{Northing} | \textit{Elevation} | Z_{xx} \textit{ data} | Z_{xy} \textit{ data} | Z_{yx} \textit{ data} | Z_{yy} \textit{ data} |$$

such that each Z_{ij} data is comprised of 4 columns:

$$| Z'_{ij} | U'_{ij} | Z''_{ij} | U''_{ij} |$$

where

- Z'_{ij} is the real component of entry i,j of the impedance tensor
- Z''_{ij} is the imaginary component of entry i,j of the impedance tensor
- U'_{ij} is the uncertainty on Z'_{ij}
- U''_{ij} is the uncertainty on Z''_{ij}

Important: For standard MT data, X = Northing, Y = Easting and Z = Down; which this code uses! Thus Z_{xy} is essentially the ratio of the electric field along the Northing and the magnetic field along the Easting. For more, see the [theory section](#).

ZTEM data (DATATYPE = MTT, MTE or MTH):

Each row in the array contains the elements of the transfer function at a particular location separated into real and imaginary components, along with the corresponding uncertainties. Data values and uncertainties are unitless with no normalization factor. [Download ZTEM data example](#) . The columns for this data format are as follows:

$$| \textit{Easting} | \textit{Northing} | \textit{Elevation} | T_{zx} \textit{ data} | T_{zy} \textit{ data} |$$

such that each T_{zx} data is comprised of 4 columns:

$$| T'_{zx} | U'_{zx} | T''_{zx} | U''_{zx} |$$

where

- T'_{zx} is the real component of T_{zx}
- T''_{zx} is the imaginary component of T_{zx}
- U'_{zx} is the uncertainty on T'_{zx}
- U''_{zx} is the uncertainty on T''_{zx}

and similarly for y .

Important: For standard natural source data, X = Northing, Y = Easting and Z = Down; which this code uses! Thus T_{zx} is the transfer function related to an incident plane wave whose electric field is polarized along the Northing direction; which produces magnetic fields with components in the Easting direction. For more, see the [theory section](#).

Important:

- If MT and/or ZTEM data are being modeled, the frequencies do not need to match nor do the locations for each frequency.
- For **MTT and MTE data (ZTEM)**, the first line in the array refers to the base/reference station location. Only the Easting, Northing and elevation is required. **However**, each remaining field must be given a flag value of “i”.
Example for first row: 350 200 0 i i i i i i i i
- For **MTH data (ZTEM)**, measurements Hx, Hy and Hz are taken at different locations. Data and uncertainty values are required for all rows.
- For **MTT and MTE data (ZTEM)**, the first line in the array refers to the base/reference station location. Thus if there are N receiver locations specified for a given array with data type “MTT”, the inversion will output $N - 1$ rows of predicted data in the predicted data files.
- For **MTH data (ZTEM)**, measurements Hx, Hy and Hz are taken at the same location. Thus if there are N receiver locations specified for a given array with data type “MTH”, the inversion model will output N rows of predicted data in the predicted data files.

3.3.4 Topography Data File

The file **topo.txt** contains all topography information. The first line in the topography file gives the number of points of known elevation followed by the list of the elevations (x,y,z). However, this is **not** the file that is used to define active topography in the forward modeling and inversion programs. Forward modeling and inversion executables require active cell models to define topography.

Fig. 3.9: Example topography file

3.3.5 Tensor Mesh File

Tensor meshes are output when creating *Octree meshes* and are used in the creation of conductivity models with *blk3cell.exe*. The format for tensor mesh files is as follows:

```

nx ny nz
x0 y0 z0
pad_lower ncx * dx pad_upper
pad_lower ncy * dy pad_upper
pad_lower ncz * dz pad_upper

```

An example of a tensor mesh file and the resulting mesh are shown below

```
tensor_mesh_test.txt - Notepad
File Edit Format View Help
30 25 10
-1.00000000E+03 -1.00000000E+03 1.50000000E+03
500 350 250 200 150 20*1.00000E+02 150 200 250 350 500
500 350 250 200 150 20*1.00000E+02
10*1.00000E+02
```

Fig. 3.10: Example tensor mesh file with different paddings in x, y and z.

Fig. 3.11: Tensor mesh generated by the file above.

Parameter Descriptions

- **nx ny nz:** The number of tensor mesh cells in the x, y and z direction
- **x0 y0 z0:** The x, y and z location denoting the **top southwest corner** of the mesh
- **ncx, ncy and ncz:** These parameters denote the number of core mesh cells in the x, y and z direction, respectively
- **dx, dy and dz:** These parameters denoted the widths of each core mesh cell in the x, y and z direction, respectively
- **pad_lower:** The individual widths of padding cells, separated by spaces, which are applied. Values should decrease from left to right. The user may leave this blank if they do not wish to pad in this direction.
- **pad_upper:** The individual widths of padding cells, separated by spaces, which are applied. Values should increase from left to right. The user may leave this blank if they do not wish to pad in this direction.

Note:

- In each direction, the number of cells (nx for example) must be equal to the total number of padding cells plus the number of core mesh cells.
 - In the z direction, the ordering of cells is from top to bottom! So *pad_lower* is padding in the up direction.
-

3.3.6 Octree Mesh File

Octree meshes define the domain for which the forward modeling or inverse problem is solved. The format of Octree mesh files is as follows:

```
nx ny nz xpL xpU ypL ypU zpL zpU
x0 y0 z0
dx dy dz
N
Lx_1 Ly_1 Lz_1 M_1
Lx_2 Ly_2 Lz_2 M_2
      ⋮
Lx_N Ly_N Lz_N M_N
```

An example of an octree mesh file is shown below

```

File Edit Format View Help
128 128 512 42 42 42 42 263 54 ! # of cells in underlying mesh, padding for onl
-2.45000000E+04 -2.45000000E+04 1.44000000E+04 ! top corner
5.00000000E+02 5.00000000E+02 1.00000000E+02 ! cell size
123148 ! size of octree mesh
1 1 1 32
33 1 1 32
65 1 1 32
97 1 1 32
1 33 1 32
33 33 1 32
65 33 1 32
97 33 1 32
1 65 1 32
33 65 1 32
65 65 1 32
97 65 1 32
1 97 1 32
33 97 1 32
65 97 1 32
97 97 1 32
1 1 33 16
17 1 33 16
33 1 33 16
49 1 33 16
65 1 33 16
81 1 33 16
97 1 33 16
113 1 33 16
1 17 33 16
17 17 33 16
33 17 33 16

```

Parameter Descriptions

- **nx ny nz:** Dimensions of the mesh in x, y and z respectively, in terms of the number of base mesh cells (cells of smallest size). Thus the mesh has dimensions $[nx \times dx, ny \times dy, nz \times dz]$.
- **xpL xpU ypL ypU zpL zpU:** These parameters set the padding distance, relative to the core region, in terms of the number of base mesh cells. For example, the region of padding cells in the southern direction (defined by *xpL*) has a width of $xpL \times dy$.
- **x0 y0 z0:** The x, y and z location denoting the **top southwest corner** of the mesh
- **dx dy dz:** Sets the x, y and z widths of the base mesh cells (smallest cells)
- **N:** Total number of cells in the mesh. Note that $nx \times ny \times nz \neq N$
- **Lx_i Ly_i Lz_i M_i:** The location and dimensions of each cell $i=1, \dots, N$ is defined by 4 parameters. Lx_i defines how many base cell widths in the x direction (i.e. dx) the top southwest corner of this cell is from the top southwest corner of the mesh plus one; i.e. the cell is $dx \times (Lx - 1)$ metres from the top southwest corner in the x direction. This is likewise for Ly_i and Lz_i . M_i defines the width of the cell in x, y and z in terms of the number of base mesh cells. Thus, the volume of each cell is $V = dx \times dy \times dz \times M^3$

Note:

- Cell locations are defined by their distances from the top southwest corner.
- See the first cell defined in the Octree mesh file (line 5). The top southwest corner if this cell corresponds with that of the mesh. However, its location is defined as 1 1 1 instead of 0 0 0 due to convention.

3.3.7 Model File

For a given model, the model file has the following format:

```
 $m_1$   
 $m_2$   
 $m_3$   
 $m_4$   
 $m_5$   
 $m_6$   
:  
 $m_{N-1}$   
 $m_N$ 
```

where N is the total number of cells in the corresponding tensor or Octree mesh.

Conductivity Models

For conductivity models, conductivity values are entered in units S/m.

Susceptibility Models

For background susceptibility models, values are entered in SI units.

Active Cells Model

Within active cells models, all cells lying below surface topography (or set as active) are given a flag value of 1. All inactive cells are given a flag value of 0.

3.3.8 Cell and Face Weights File

Cell Weights

Cell weights files have the same format as *model files*. When creating cells weights:

- All cells must be assigned a weight values larger than 0! This is to ensure the problem is sufficiently well-conditioned.
- Model weight values should be set relative to a value of 1. This is to ensure the relative emphasis on model weights and surface weights is preserved. A value of 1 implies that no cell weighting is being applied.
- Large model weights ($w \gg 1$) are used for cells that we want to match the reference model.
- Small model weights ($w \ll 1$) are used for cells to reduce the impact of the reference model on the cells.

Interface Weights

Interface weights files contain the interface weights in x, y and z in a single column vectors; as the number of faces in x, y and z may differ. When creating interface weights:

- All interface weights must be larger than 0! This is to ensure the problem is sufficiently well-conditioned.
- Interface weight value should be set relative to a value of 1. This is to ensure the relative emphasis on model weights and surface weights is preserved. A value of 1 implies that no interface weighting is being applied.
- Large interface weights ($w \gg 1$) preserve gradients within reference model.
- Small interface weights ($w \ll 1$) results in smoother gradients within

RUNNING THE PROGRAMS

This section provides describes how to run all executables pertaining to the E3DMT version 1 package.

Note: All executable files, input files, output filenames and files specified within input files can be specified in the following manner:

- as just the filename if contained within the current working directory (Example: *filename.txt*)
- as a file path relative to the current working directory (Example: *sub_dir\filename.txt*)
- as the full path (Example: *C:\Users\Name\Tests\filename.txt*)

Executable files should **not** be renamed. However, input file names can be specified by the user if desired.

4.1 Executables

Important: Although described here, this generation of the code may not be supported by GIFtools in the future.

The main executable programs within the E3DMT version 1 program library are:

- **e3dmt_fwd:** Solves the forward problem. Computes the electric and magnetic response to a 3D conductivity model (fields, and impedance)
- **e3dmt:** Solves the inverse problem using a direct solver approach (MUMPS). Recovers a conductivity model by inverting MT or ZTEM data. All entries of the impedance tensor or transfer function are needed.
- **e3dmt_iter:** Solves the inverse problem using an iterative solver approach. Recovers a conductivity model by inverting MT or ZTEM data. All entries of the impedance tensor or transfer function are needed.
- **create_octree_mesh_e3dmt:** Creates an octree mesh based on the *survey file*

Common Octree utility programs used with this package include:

- **blk3cell:** Creates models from a set of blocks on a tensor mesh
- **3DModel2Octree:** Converts models from tensor to Octree meshes
- **interface_weights:** Creates interface weights

4.2 Contents

To learn the specifics of running each executable, see the following sections:

4.2.1 Create OcTree Mesh

OcTree meshes used in the E3DMT version 1 code are created using the program **create_octree_mesh_e3dmt.exe**. Parameters necessary for defining the OcTree mesh are set in the *input file*; referred to here as **octree_mesh.inp**.

To generate the OcTree mesh, open a command window. Type the path to the code **create_octree_mesh_e3dmt.exe**, followed by a space, followed by the path to the input file.

```
C:\UBC>create_octree_mesh_e3dmt octree_mesh.inp
```

The program **create_octree_mesh_e3dmt.exe** creates 5 output files:

- **3D_mesh.txt**: the underlying regular *tensor mesh*. This mesh is comprised of the smallest cell size and is very large (>> 1M cells). As a result, it is unwise to plot this mesh.
- **3D_core_mesh.txt**: A 3D regular *tensor mesh* defining the core region.
- **octree_mesh.txt**: *OcTree mesh* used in the forward modeling and inversion codes
- **active_cells.txt**: *active cells model* on the OcTree mesh. Cells are active if assigned a value of 1 and inactive if assigned a value of 0
- **create_mesh.log**: log file

4.2.2 Create Model

Models (conductivity/susceptibility/active) used within the forward modeling and inversion codes are generated by carrying out a 2-step process. First, the program **blk3cell.exe** is executed to create a model on the base 3D *tensor mesh* (**3D_mesh.txt**) which was output by the code *create_octree_mesh_e3dmt.exe*; see *outputs*. This model is comprised of a set of overlapping rectangular blocks whose locations, dimensions and values are specified within the *input file*; referred to as **blk3cell.inp**.

Next, **3Dmodel2octree.exe** is used to interpolate the tensor model onto an *OcTree mesh*. The tensor mesh (**3D_mesh.txt**), tensor *model* (**3Dmodel.con**) and octree mesh (**octree_mesh.txt**) are all specified in another *input file*; referred to here as **3Dmodel2octree.inp**.

Note: This workflow can also be used to create a *model weights* file.

Running blk3cell

To generate the tensor model on the core tensor mesh, open a command window. In order, enter the path to **blk3cell.exe**, followed by the path to the tensor mesh file name (**3D_mesh.txt**), followed by the path to the *input file* (denoted here as **blk3cell.inp**), followed by the desired name (or full path) for the output model file (denoted here as **3Dmodel.con**), all separated by spaces.

```
C:\Users\ubcgif>blk3cell.exe 3D_mesh.txt blk3cell.inp 3Dmodel.con
```

blk3cell.exe outputs a *model* (**3Dmodel.con**) which contains a single value for each cell in the tensor mesh **3D_mesh.txt**.

Warning: It is not advisable to image models on the base tensor mesh as they can be prohibitively large (>> 1M cells).

Running 3Dmodel2Octree

To interpolate the model from a *tensor mesh* to an *Octree mesh*, open a command window. Enter the path to **3DModel2Octree.exe** followed by a space followed by the path to the *input file*; referred to here as **3Dmodel2octree.inp**.

```
C:\Users\ubcgif>3DModel2Octree.exe 3Dmodel2octree.inp
```

3Dmodel2Octree.exe outputs a *model file* (**Output model name**) which has been interpolated from the base *tensor mesh* to the *Octree mesh*.

4.2.3 Forward Modeling Program

The forward problem is solved using the executable program **e3dmt_fwd.exe**. Parameters necessary for running the forward modeling code are set in the *input file*; denoted here as **e3dmtfwd.inp**.

Running the Program

To run the forward modeling program, open a command line window. Type the path to the code **e3dmt_fwd.exe**, followed by a space, followed by the path to the *input file*.

```
C:\UBC>e3dmt_fwd.exe e3dmtfwd.inp
```

Units:

Inputs:

- **Conductivity model:** S/m
- **Background susceptibility model:** SI

Outputs:

- **MT data:** Real and imaginary components of impedance tensor entries (V/A)
- **ZTEM data:** Real and imaginary components of transfer function entries (unitless)

Output Files

The program `e3dmt_fwd.exe` creates 2 output files:

- **MT_data.txt:** data predicted using the conductivity model provided
- **e3dmt.log:** log file

4.2.4 Create Additional Cell and Face Weights

The creation of specific cell and face weights is not required to run the inversion. However, the user may want to weight the relative contributions of cells and/or gradients in certain regions towards the model objective function; see *theory: inversion*. The user may also want to apply weights that reduce the impact of near surface artifacts due to receivers.

Generating Model Weights File

Model weights are applied in the smallness term of the model objective function; see *theory: inversion*. To generate a model weights file, use the same workflow described on the *create model* page. When creating a model weight file, consider the following:

- All cells **must** be assigned a weight values larger than 0! This is to ensure the problem is sufficiently well-conditioned.
- Model weight values should be set relative to a value of 1. This is to ensure the relative emphasis on model weights and surface weights is preserved.
- Large model weights ($w \gg 1$) are used for cells that we want to match the reference model. Small model weights ($w \ll 1$) are used for cells to reduce the impact of the reference model on the cells.

Generating Interface Weights File

Interface weights are used to preserve the gradients or edges within certain regions of the reference model. They are also used to reduce near-surface artifacts which result from the sensitivity to the receiver locations. Interface weights are applied within the gradient terms of the model objective function; see *theory: inversion*. When creating interface weights, consider the following:

- All interface weights **must** be larger than 0! This is to ensure the problem is sufficiently well-conditioned.
- Interface weight values should be set relative to a value of 1. This is to ensure the relative emphasis on model weights and surface weights is preserved.

- Large interface weights ($w \gg 1$) preserve gradients within reference model. Small interface weights ($w \ll 1$) results in smoother gradients within the recovered model.

To generate interface weights on an Octree mesh, open a command window. In order, enter the path to `interface_weights.exe`, followed by the path to the *input file*; denoted here as `interface_weights.inp`:

```
C:\Users\ubcgif>interface_weights.exe interface_weights.inp
```

Output File

The executable outputs an `interface_weights` file with the specified output name. This file stores the interface weights in X, Y and Z in a single column; as the number of faces in the X, Y and Z direction are likely different.

4.2.5 Inversion Program

There are two options for inversion executables, both of which require parameters set through an *input file*; denoted here as `e3dmt.inp`. The two executable files are:

- `e3dmt.exe`: Uses the MUMPS direct solver. Faster but larger memory requirements
- `e3dmt_iter.exe`: Uses an iterative solver. Slower run-time but less memory requirements

Running the Program

Here, the `mpiexec` call is used to parallelize multiple processes (large-scale independent operations) within the code. To run the executable, open a command window and type the following:

```
C:\UBC>mpiexec -n "nFreq" e3dmt_iter.exe e3dmt.inp
```

The call `mpiexec` is followed by the flag `-n`, then the number of processes ("*nFreq*") to be carried out simultaneously. This is followed by the paths to the executable and the corresponding input file, respectively. The number of simultaneous processes ("*nFreq*") **must** be equal or less than the number of frequencies. Ideally there is enough memory for `nFreq` to be equal to the number of frequencies.

Setting the Number of Threads with Open MPI

Before running the executable, the number of threads used to carry out all simultaneous processes can be set with Open MPI. This is set in the command window **before** running the executable. To set the number of threads (*nThreads*), use the following syntax:

- Windows computer: "set OMP_NUM_THREADS=*nThreads*"
- Linux (bash shell): "export OMP_NUM_THREADS=*nThreads*"
- Linux (csh shell): "setenv OMP_NUM_THREADS *nThreads*"

Units

Inputs:

- **MT data:** Real and imaginary components of impedance tensor entries (V/A)
- **ZTEM data:** Real and imaginary components of transfer function entries (unitless)
- **Reference/starting conductivity model:** S/m
- **Background susceptibility model:** SI
- **Model/interface weights:** unitless

Important: The current version of the code requires both components for all entries within the impedance tensor. For example, the user cannot invert only the off-diagonal impedance tensor data. Instead the user must supply large uncertainties for the diagonal data.

Outputs:

- **Conductivity model:** S/m

Output Files

The program **e3dMTinv.exe** creates the following output files:

- **inv.con:** recovered conductivity models
- **dpred.txt** predicted data for each recovered conductivity model
- **e3dmt.log:** log file for the inversion
- **e3dmt.out:**

EXAMPLES

Here, the program libraries for E3DMT version 1 will be used to:

- create an Octree mesh based on the survey
- create octree models
- predict MT or ZTEM data for a synthetic model
- invert MT or ZTEM data created using our synthetic model

5.1 Magnetotellurics

Zip folders containing all necessary files for the magnetotelluric example can be downloaded here:

- [Files for example](#)

The full example is parsed into 4 sections:

5.1.1 Create OcTree Mesh

Here, the code `create_octree_mesh_e3dmt.exe` and the input file `octree_mesh.inp` (*see format*) are used to create an OcTree mesh based on the set of observation location and surface topography. In our case, we set the topography to have a constant elevation of 0 m. Files relevant to this part of the example are in the sub-folder `octree_mesh`. Before running this example, you may want to do the following:

- [Download and open the zip folder containing the entire E3DMT version 1 example \(if not done already\)](#)
- [Learn how to run code from command line](#)
- [Learn the format of the input file](#)

To generate the OcTree mesh, the following input file was used:

The resulting OcTree mesh and surface topography are shown below.

```

octree_mesh.inp (~\Documents\Reposit...\e3dmt\assets\input_files_ver1) - GVIM
File Edit Tools Syntax Buffers Window Help
[Icons]
200 200 100          ! min dx
5000 5000 5000 5000 ! padding x, y, down, air
1600 800 800        ! depths for area of interest
4 4 4              ! # of small cells around receivers
ONLY_LOC input_files\dataPoints.txt ! Survey (data locations) file
TOPO_CONST 0        ! topo file | TOPO_CONST val
NOT_SHIFT_DATA      ! SHIFT_DATA | NOT_SHIFT_DATA
APPROXTOPO          ! APPROXTOPO | GOODTOPO
START_LARGE_CELLS   ! START_LARGE_CELLS | START_SMALL_CELLS
                                     1,1      All
    
```


5.1.2 Create Model

Here, the code `blk3cell.exe` and the input file `blk3cell.inp` (*see format*) are used to create a conductivity model on the underlying tensor mesh. Then, the code `3DModel2Octree.exe` and the input file `3Dmodel2octree.inp` (*see format*) are used to interpolate the tensor mesh onto the OcTree mesh. For this example, we use the mesh that was created in the example “*create OcTree mesh*”. Files relevant to this part of the example are in the sub-folder `octree_model`. Before running this example, you may want to do the following:

- Download and open the zip folder containing the entire E3DMT version 1 example (if not done already)
- Learn how to run `blk3cell` and `3DModel2Octree` from command line
- Learn the format of the input files `blk3cell.inp` and `3Dmodel2octree.inp`

Here is the input file for `blk3cell.exe`

```

0.01 ! background
3 ! number of blocks
3400 4600 1600 4600 -400 -1200 1.
1600 4600 3400 4600 -400 -1200 1.
-999999 999999 -999999 999999 999999 0 1.e-8
1,1 All

```

Warning: It is not advisable to image models on the base tensor mesh as they can be prohibitively large (>> 1M cells).

Here is the input file for `3DModel2Octree.exe`

```

LOG_MODEL ! LOG_MODEL | LIN_MODEL
input_files\octree_mesh.txt ! input octree mesh file
input_files\3D_mesh.txt ! input 3D mesh
output_files\3Dmodel.con ! input 3D model
USE_INPUT_MESH ! output octree mesh file
octree_model.con ! output octree model file
START_LARGE_CELLS ! START_LARGE_CELLS | START_SMALL_CELLS
1,1 All

```

The resulting Octree model shows an L-shaped conductor ($\sigma = 1$ S/m) within a resistive background ($\sigma_b = 0.01$ S/m).

5.1.3 Forward Modeling

Here, the code `e3dmt_fwd.exe` and the input file `e3dmtfwd.inp` (*see format*) are used to forward model MT data for a synthetic model. Files relevant to this part of the example are in the sub-folder `fwd`. For this example, we use the model that was created in the example “*create model*”. Before running this example, you may want to do the following:

- Download and open the zip folder containing the entire E3DMT version 1 example (if not done already)
- *Learn how to run code from command line*
- *Learn the format of the input file*

To forward model the data, the following input file was used:

```
e3dmtfwd.inp (~\Documents\Repositories\e3dmt\assets\input_files_ver1) - GVIM
File Edit Tools Syntax Buffers Window Help
input_files/octree_mesh.txt      ! octree mesh file
input_files/dataPoints.txt      ! locations file
input_files/octree_model.con     ! real conductivity model | VALUE
NO_IMAG_COND                    ! imaginary conductivity model | NO_IMAG_COND
VALUE 0.01                      ! 1D background conductivity file | VALUE #
NO_SUS                           ! background susceptibility model | NO_SUS
input_files/active_cells_topo.txt ! topography active cell file | ALL_ACTIVE
                                  1,1      All
```

Predicted data are shown below.

5.1.4 Inversion

Here, the code `e3dmt.exe` and the input file `e3dmt.inp` (*see format*) are used to invert MT data. MT data were created in the example “*forward modeling*”. Uncertainties of 0.001 V/A +/- 5% were added to all off diagonal impedance tensor elements. Uncertainties of 0.0005 V/A +/- 5% were added to all diagonal impedance tensor elements. In practice, data are noisy and choosing appropriate uncertainties is very important for successful inversion. Files relevant to this part of the example are in the sub-folder `inv`. Before running this example, you may want to do the following:

- Download and open the zip folder containing the entire E3DMT version 1 example (if not done already)
- *Learn how to run code from command line*
- *Learn the format of the input file*

To invert the synthetic data, the input file below was used:

```

e3dmt.inp (~\Documents\Repositories\e3dmt\assets\input_files_ver1) - GVIM
File Edit Tools Syntax Buffers Window Help
input_files/octree_mesh.txt      ! mesh file
input_files/MT_data.dat         ! data file
VALUE 0.01                      ! 1d background
VALUE 0.01                      ! initial model
VALUE 0.01                      ! reference model
NO_SUS                          ! background susceptibility model | NO_SUS
input_files/active_cells_topo.txt ! topography active cell file | ALL_ACTIVE
ALL_ACTIVE                     ! model active cell file | ALL_ACTIVE
NO_WEIGHT                       ! cell weight file | NO_WEIGHT | EKBLUM
NO_FACE_WEIGHT                 ! face weighting file | NO_FACE_WEIGHT
0.1 1e-6 0.2                   ! DEFAULT ! beta_max beta_min beta_factor
2.5e-5 1 1 0.25                ! alpha_s alpha_x alpha_y alpha_z
0.6                             ! chifact
1.e-2 1.e-3 3                  ! tol_nl mindm iter_per_beta
1.e-2 20                       ! tol_ipcg max_iter_ipcg
NOT_CHANGE_MREF                ! CHANGE_MREF | NOT_CHANGE_MREF
SMOOTH_MOD_DIF                 ! SMOOTH_MOD | SMOOTH_MOD_DIF
BOUNDS_NONE                    ! BOUNDS_CONST 1.e-10 1.e+10 ! BOUNDS_NONE
1e-11 1e-5 150 1e6            ! tol_bicg tol_ipcg_bicg max_it_bicg freq_Aphi (iterative only)
                                     1,1      All

```

The true model (left) and recovered model (right) are shown below. A cutoff of 0.1 S/m has been used for both models and the recovered model is transected horizontally at $z = -500$ m.

5.2 ZTEM

Zip folders containing all necessary files for the ZTEM example can be downloaded here:

- [Files for example](#)

The full example is parsed into 4 sections:

5.2.1 Create OcTree Mesh

Here, the code `create_octree_mesh_e3dmt.exe` and the input file `octree_mesh.inp` (*see format*) are used to create an OcTree mesh based on the set of observation location and surface topography. In our case, we set the topography to have a constant elevation of 0 m. Files relevant to this part of the example are in the sub-folder `octree_mesh`. Before running this example, you may want to do the following:

- [Download and open the zip folder containing the entire E3DMT version 1 example](#) (if not done already)
- [Learn how to run code from command line](#)
- [Learn the format of the input file](#)

To generate the OcTree mesh, the following input file was used:

```

200 200 100      ! min dx
5000 5000 5000 5000 ! padding x, y, down, air
1600 800 800    ! depths for area of interest
4 4 4          ! # of small cells around receivers
ONLY_LOC input_files\dataPoints.txt ! Survey (data locations) file
TOPO_CONST 0    ! topo file | TOPO_CONST val
NOT_SHIFT_DATA ! SHIFT_DATA | NOT_SHIFT_DATA
APPROXTOPO     ! APPROXTOPO | GOODTOPO
START_LARGE_CELLS ! START_LARGE_CELLS | START_SMALL_CELLS
1,1           All

```

The resulting OcTree mesh and surface topography are shown below.

5.2.2 Create Model

Here, the code `blk3cell.exe` and the input file `blk3cell.inp` (*see format*) are used to create a conductivity model on the underlying tensor mesh. Then, the code `3DModel2OcTree.exe` and the input file `3Dmodel2octree.inp` (*see format*) are used to interpolate the tensor mesh onto the OcTree mesh. For this example, we use the mesh that was created in the example “*create OcTree mesh*”. Files relevant to this part of the example are in the sub-folder `octree_model`. Before running this example, you may want to do the following:

- [Download and open the zip folder containing the entire E3DMT version 1 example](#) (if not done already)
- [Learn how to run `blk3cell` and `3DModel2OcTree` from command line](#)
- [Learn the format of the input files `blk3cell.inp` and `3Dmodel2octree.inp`](#)

Here is the input file for `blk3cell.exe`


```
blk3cell.inp (~\Documents\Repos...mt\assets\input_files_ver1) - GVIM
File Edit Tools Syntax Buffers Window Help
[Icons]
0.01  ! background
3      ! number of blocks
3400  4600  1600  4600  -400  -1200  1.
1600  4600  3400  4600  -400  -1200  1.
-999999 999999 -999999 999999 999999 0 1.e-8
1,1 All
```

Warning: It is not advisable to image models on the base tensor mesh as they can be prohibitively large (>> 1M cells).

Here is the input file for **3DModel2Octree.exe**


```

LOG_MODEL          ? LOG_MODEL | LIN_MODEL
input_files\octree_mesh.txt  ? input octree mesh file
input_files\3D_mesh.txt     ? input 3D mesh
output_files\3Dmodel.con    ? input 3D model
USE_INPUT_MESH           ? output octree mesh file
octree_model.con          ? output octree model file
START_LARGE_CELLS       ? START_LARGE_CELLS | START_SMALL_CELLS
                        1,1
                        All
  
```

The resulting Octree model shows an L-shaped conductor ($\sigma = 1$ S/m) within a resistive background ($\sigma_b = 0.01$ S/m).

5.2.3 Forward Modeling

Here, the code **e3dmt_fwd.exe** and the input file **e3dmtfwd.inp** (*see format*) are used to forward model ZTEM data for a synthetic model. Files relevant to this part of the example are in the sub-folder *fwd*. For this example, we use the model that was created in the example “*create model*”. Before running this example, you may want to do the following:

- Download and open the zip folder containing the entire E3DMT version 1 example (if not done already)
- *Learn how to run code from command line*
- *Learn the format of the input file*

To forward model the data, the following input file was used:


```
e3dmtfwd.inp (~\Documents\Repositories\e3dmt\assets\input_files_ver1) - GVIM
File Edit Tools Syntax Buffers Window Help
input_files/octree_mesh.txt ! octree mesh file
input_files/dataPoints.txt ! locations file
input_files/octree_model.con ! real conductivity model | VALUE
NO_IMAG_COND ! imaginary conductivity model | NO_IMAG_COND
VALUE 0.01 ! 1D background conductivity file | VALUE #
NO_SUS ! background susceptibility model | NO_SUS
input_files/active_cells_topo.txt ! topography active cell file | ALL_ACTIVE
1,1 All
```

Predicted data are shown below.

5.2.4 Inversion

Here, the code **e3dmt.exe** and the input file **e3dmt.inp** (*see format*) are used to invert ZTEM data. ZTEM data were created in the example “*forward modeling*”. Uncertainties of 0.01 +/- 5% were added to tipper data at 10 Hz and 50 Hz. Uncertainties of 0.005 +/- 5% were added to tipper data at 200 Hz. In practice, data are noisy and choosing appropriate uncertainties is very important for successful inversion. Files relevant to this part of the example are in the sub-folder *inv*. Before running this example, you may want to do the following:

- Download and open the zip folder containing the entire E3DMT version 1 example (if not done already)
- *Learn how to run code from command line*
- *Learn the format of the input file*

To invert the synthetic data, the input file below was used:

The true model (left) and recovered model (right) are shown below. A cutoff of 0.1 S/m has been used for both models and the recovered model is transected horizontally at $z = -400$ m.


```

e3dmt.inp (~\Documents\Repositories\e3dmt\assets\input_files_ver1) - GVIM
File Edit Tools Syntax Buffers Window Help
input_files/octree_mesh.txt      ! mesh file
input_files/MT_data.dat        ! data file
VALUE 0.01                      ! 1d background
VALUE 0.01                      ! initial model
VALUE 0.01                      ! reference model
NO_SUS                          ! background susceptibility model | NO_SUS
input_files/active_cells_topo.txt ! topography active cell file | ALL_ACTIVE
ALL_ACTIVE                      ! model active cell file | ALL_ACTIVE
NO_WEIGHT                       ! cell weight file | NO_WEIGHT | EKBLOM
NO_FACE_WEIGHT                 ! face weighting file | NO_FACE_WEIGHT
0.1 1e-6 0.2                   ! DEFAULT ! beta_max beta_min beta_factor
2.5e-5 1 1 0.25               ! alpha_s alpha_x alpha_y alpha_z
0.6                             ! chifact
1.e-2 1.e-3 3                 ! tol_nl mindm iter_per_beta
1.e-2 20                       ! tol_ipcg max_iter_ipcg
NOT_CHANGE_MREF                ! CHANGE_MREF | NOT_CHANGE_MREF
SMOOTH_MOD_DIF                 ! SMOOTH_MOD | SMOOTH_MOD_DIF
BOUNDS_NONE                    ! BOUNDS_CONST 1.e-10 1.e+10 ! BOUNDS_NONE
1e-11 1e-5 150 1e6            ! tol_bicg tol_ipcg_bicg max_it_bicg freq_Aphi (iterative only)
                                     1,1      All
  
```


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